
TEACHING AND ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING A LANGUAGE AT A TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7972413>

Khalilova Olima Akhatovna

*The senior teacher of Foreign Language department, Karshi Engineering Economic
Institute*

olimaahatovna67@gmail.com

Abstract.

Independence in educational activities is expressed in the need and ability to think independently, navigate in a new situation, see the task and find an approach to its solution. This article discusses the preparation and organization of independent work of students in the process of learning a language in a technical university.

Keywords.

foreign language teaching, student-centered education, communicative situations, independent work.

Introduction:

Today, ways to increase the effectiveness of foreign language teaching in higher education establishments are actively developing. The search for ways to increase the cognitive activity of students in the context of foreign language education is carried out by many scientists from different positions. One of the available and justified ways to increase the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language is to organize independent teaching work. With the introduction of a new generation of state educational standards, the importance of independent work in the process of learning a foreign language is increasing significantly [20, 3518]. Mandatory use of this type of work depends on the requirements of personal competence development, which includes the following skills and abilities: independent goal setting; operational planning; their implementation; correlation of the result with the goal; adjustment (if necessary). This is possible under a number of conditions:

- 1) According to the reorganization of the educational process according to the educational component;
- 2) Improvement of educational and methodological documents;

3) Introduction of new information and educational technologies;

4) Technical updating and software support for independent work;

5) New technology of self-control and current control of knowledge, skills and property. In this regard, part of the work of teachers changes qualitatively, which is reflected in their personal plans in terms of educational and educational-methodical work²²⁷. Review of the inner essence of independent work, aimed at the development of personal independence, is based on the theory of student-oriented education. This approach allows a person to maximize their intellectual abilities and learn how to work in a team. In the context of learning a foreign language, first, it is necessary to draw a conclusion from the fact that if language is a means of communication, and speech is a means of this interaction, then it is possible to master the way of communication. Only when creating conditions for personality-oriented communicative situations. Only in the conditions of a student-oriented approach and individualization of education is a new quality of research on the problem of filling the internal content of independent learning activities. The essence of students' independent work is that students develop their abilities independently through learning a foreign language. Awareness of students' needs and preferred learning style makes the learning process more effective. In addition, independent work involves the development of the student's ability to determine independently the tasks and methods of education, conduct introspection. A student should be interested in learning a foreign language, know his potential and try to overcome the limitations of his abilities.

Literature review:

In modern didactics, the concept of "independent work" necessarily correlates with its organizing, guiding, corrective role. Methodists in the field of teaching foreign languages give a different interpretation of the concept of "independent work". In the broadest sense, independent work is characterized as a combination of various types of educational activities of students [38, 224]. Independent work is also understood as the individual and collective work of students carried out by them in the classroom or at home without the direct participation of the teacher, but on his instructions, at a specified time; at the same time, students consciously achieve the goal, using their knowledge and expressing the result of mental or physical actions [42, 32]. M.G. Garunov and P.I. Pidkasty emphasize that "independent work forms the student at each stage of his movement from ignorance to knowledge the necessary volume and level of knowledge, skills and

²²⁷ Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. TECHNOLOGY IN LANGUAGE TEACHING. ajps [Internet]. 2022 Nov. 8 [cited 2023 Apr. 24];2(11):11-6. Available from: <https://theusajournals.com/index.php/ajps/article/view/460>.

abilities to solve cognitive problems; develops in the trainee a psychological attitude to the systematic replenishment of his knowledge and the development of skills to navigate in the flow of scientific information" [37, 18]. Thus, "independent work can be considered as one of the types of cognitive activity aimed at general educational and special training of students and managed by the teacher".

Analysis:The following features characterize students who have the skills of independent work: A positive attitude to learning, which is necessary for mastering a foreign language; knowledge of some techniques in the study of a foreign language; possession of communication strategies; The formation of intercultural communicative competence Independent work not only increases the cognitive activity of students, but also has another important advantage - it is individual in nature. Thanks to this property, independent work takes on a flexible adaptive character, thus contributing to an increase in the responsibility of students and, consequently, their academic performance [11, 133].

Independent work allows students to try and find for themselves the most effective ways of perceiving and mastering the material, to form their own cognitive style in the process of learning a foreign language, taking into account individual characteristics of thinking. The development of the above skills and training strategies is most effective in the conditions of alternating different types of independent work of students. In modern methodology, there are many principles for classifying the autonomous learning activities of students. Some researchers divide it according to goals, others - according to the nature of the learning tasks performed by the trainees on their own, others take as a basis the nature of learning activities in the process of solving various problems²²⁸.

In the process of teaching independent work, students perform tasks that the teacher offered them in the course of explaining new material. As a result of the performance of such work, it is immediately clear whether the material has been mastered by the students or not, difficult moments are revealed, and gaps in knowledge that prevent them from firmly mastering the material being studied also make themselves felt. The teacher needs to know the following features of teaching independent work: it must be composed mainly of tasks of an unproductive nature, checked immediately and not put bad marks. Timely verification of the results gives the teacher a clear picture of the degree of understanding of the new material by the students at the earliest stage of training. The purpose of this work is not control, but training, so it should be given a lot of

²²⁸ Khalilova OA. Organizational Aspects of Developing Innovative Methods in Teaching. Eastern European Scientific Journal. 2018 Apr 10(2). <http://journale.auris-verlag.de/index.php/EESJ/article/viewFile/891/965>

time in the classroom. The training type of independent work includes tasks for the recognition of various objects and properties. They consist of tasks of the same type, containing the essential features and properties of a given definition, rules where they need to reproduce or directly apply the knowledge gained in practice. This includes the performance of tasks on multi-level cards that teach students to work independently. This type of independent work is especially favorable for less motivated students, as they are more easily involved in the work and cope with it.

The reinforcing type of independent work includes tasks that contribute to the development of logical thinking and require the combined application of various rules. They show how well the learning material is learned. Based on the results of checking assignments of this type, the teacher determines whether it is still necessary to deal with this topic. Examples of such works are found in abundance in the didactic material.²²⁹

Independent work of a developing nature can be offered in the form of reports on certain topics, preparation for Olympiads, scientific and creative conferences, etc. As a rule, students approach creative tasks with great interest, because here they can apply all their knowledge, implement ideas, demonstrate creativity. Analyzing the creative work of his wards, the teacher can find a new version of how it is easier and more interesting to convey a certain topic to students, based on their vision of this issue. Control works are a necessary condition for achieving the planned learning outcomes. Assignments of control works should:

- be equivalent in content and volume of work;
- be aimed at developing basic skills;
- provide reliable verification of the level of knowledge;
- be of increasing complexity, and are also made taking into account the individual characteristics of students [5, 130].

The main advantage of independent work is that collective work is possible here to achieve a common goal, solving common tasks that encourage cooperation. Intermediate and final results of independent activity can be successfully discussed by all students, as well as mutually controlled. This has a significant impact on the quality of knowledge and skills, stimulates the cognitive interest and activity of students. With the competent guidance of the teacher, independent work is of great educational importance. If the whole class performs one task, the cognitive

²²⁹ Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Main components of organizing independent work of students // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/main-components-of-organizing-independent-work-of-students>(дата обращения: 05.05.2023).

process acquires some features of collective activity. When discussing the results of such work, a common opinion is quickly developed, a single position in relation to the material being studied, which creates the basis for collective experiences, the formation of students' views and beliefs.

Conclusion: Thus, the new standards focus on student-centered approach to learning. Successful teaching of technical university subjects, and foreign languages in particular, is impossible without intensive independent work of students. The development of independent activity is one of the most important ways of forming a holistic, harmoniously developed personality.

These qualities are formed only under the condition of the systematic inclusion of learning in an independent activity, which in the process of implementation acquires the character of a problem-search activity.

REFERENCES:

49. AMINOVA ZP, KHALILOVA OA. MATERIALS IN ESP COURSES. Иностранные языки в Узбекистане. 2019(3):83-93. <https://journal.fledu.uz/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2019/08/article-5604-1507.pdf>.
50. Badalova, L. (2022). Development of the cognitive interest of students in teaching a foreign language at a technical university. Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 174–176. <http://conferenceseries.info/index.php/online/article/view/79>.
51. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna. (2022). Formation of Intercultural Competence in Teaching the Translation of Economic Texts. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, 6, 14–19. Retrieved from <https://geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejlat/article/view/801>.
52. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS // ORIENSS. 2021. №5. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/innovative-methods-of-teaching-in-educational-institution>.
53. Badalova Luiza Kholmamatovna. (2022). NEW TRENDS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS FOREIGN LANGUAGE. Open Access Repository, 8(03), 130–133. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/RK8HX>.
54. Khalilova OA. Teaching speaking: examples of oral communicative activities. Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука. 2017(2 (2)):32-4. <https://www.inter-nauka.com/uploads/public/1490953057675.pdf#page=33>.

55. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. (2023). STYLISTICS AND STYLE: A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE AND RECENT TRENDS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 607–610. Retrieved from <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3858>.

56. Khalilova O.A. FUNDAMENTALS OF LEXICOLOGY // Экономика и социум. 2021. №3-1 (82). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/fundamentals-of-lexicology> (дата обращения: 12.04.2023).

57. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. (2022). Teaching Pronunciation Skills. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 5, 279–282. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjm/article/view/888>.

58. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna, Obzorov Islom Ruzievich. Prospects of the energy system in Uzbekistan. *Int J Appl Res* 2020;6(5):306-307. <https://www.allresearchjournal.com/archives/?year=2020&vol=6&issue=5&part=E&ArticleId=6717>.

59. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. (2023). CLT PLAY AN IMPORTANT ROLE TO LEARN LANGUAGE EFFECTIVELY. *World Bulletin of Management and Law*, 21, 133-136. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbml/article/view/2571>.

60. Khalilova OA. Organizational Aspects of Developing Innovative Methods in Teaching. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*. 2018 Apr 10(2). <http://journale.auris-verlag.de/index.php/EESJ/article/viewFile/891/965>.

61. Khalilova Olima Akhatovna. TECHNOLOGY IN LANGUAGE TEACHING. *ajps* [Internet]. 2022 Nov. 8 [cited 2023 Apr. 24];2(11):11-6. Available from: <https://theusajournals.com/index.php/ajps/article/view/460>.

62. Khujanovich, E. U. (2023). The Effectiveness of using Mobile Applications in Teaching a Foreign Language. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 32, 288–292. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1150>.

63. Madaminovich, T. I., Khusanovich, K. B., Akhatovna, K. O., & Kholmamatovna, B. L. (2019). Features of the System of Formation of Compensatory Competence Among Agricultural Students as a Means of Filling in Professional Terminology. In *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering* (Vol. 8, Issue 11, pp. 2202–2206). Blue Eyes Intelligence Engineering and Sciences Engineering and Sciences Publication - BEIESP. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijitee.k2039.0981119>.

64. Mansurova Gulbahor Makhdievna. (2022). Teaching the Interpretation of a Literary Text in German Lessons. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic*

Teaching, 6, 27-31. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejlat/article/view/803>.

65. Mansurova, G. M., & Fayzieva, K. A. (2020). GENERAL CRITERIA FOR THE EVALUATION CATEGORY. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University, 2(8), 227-230. https://scholar.google.ru/scholar?hl=ru&as_sdt=0,5&cluster=1242523419625242789.

66. Mansurova, Gulbahor and Fayzieva, Kamila (2019) "EVALUATION CATEGORY IN FOREIGN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES ACCORDING TO THEIR PRAGMATIC CHARACTERISTICS." Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University: Vol. 1: Iss. 2, Article 41. Available at: <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/namdu/vol1/iss2/41>

67. Mansurova GM, Eshonkulova NT, Eshmurodov UK. THE TRAGEDY OF "JULIUS CAESAR". Социосфера. 2021(1):54-6. http://www.sociosfera.com/files/conference/2021/sociosfera_1-21.pdf#page=55.

68. Mirkhaydarovna, J. S., Irkinovna, D. N., Abdimuminovna, C. S., Shamsievna, I. P., & Kholmamatovna, B. L. (2023). Intensive Methods of Improving Linguistic Competence in the Russian Language of Students of Non-Linguistic Higher Education Institutions in Uzbekistan. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 10(2S), 3518-3528. [Intensive Methods of Improving Linguistic Competence in the Russian Language of Students of Non-Linguistic Higher Education Institutions in Uzbekistan | Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences \(sifisheressciences.com\)](https://www.sifisheressciences.com).

69. Niyazova Yulduz Tashmuradovna. (2023). GAMIFICATION IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities. FARS Publishers, 11(2), 912-917. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7689661>.

70. Niyazova Yu. T. Comprehend simple grammatical errors and effective ways of teaching grammar / Yu. T. Niyazova // Міжнародний науковий журнал "Інтернаука" . - 2017. - № 5. - С. 43-44. - Режим доступу: http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/mnj_2017_5_12.

71. Niyazova, Y. (2022). BASIC PRINCIPLES OF LISTENING TECHNOLOGY. *Scientific Collection «InterConf»*, (110), 93-98. Retrieved from <https://archive.interconf.center/index.php/conference-proceeding/article/view/455>.

72. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Main components of organizing independent work of students // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/main-components-of-organizing-independent-work-of-students>(дата обращения: 05.05.2023).

73. Soliyeva Munavvar Akhmadovna Some features of effective teaching professionally oriented foreign language // Достижения науки и образования. 2017. №4 (17). URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/some-features-of-effective-teaching-professionally-oriented-foreign-language>(дата обращения: 30.03.2023).

74. Solieva Munavvar Ahmadovna 2022. Appeal in the Structure of Speech Etiquette. International Journal on Integrated Education. 5, 6 (Jun. 2022), 158-161. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v5i6.3143>.

75. Tashmuradovna , N. Y. . (2023). The Function of Phrasal Verbs as Lexical Material in Business English. Miasto Przyszłości, 32, 272–276. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/1146>.

76. Umedilloevna, S. M. UDC: 1751 Lexicographic Analysis Of The Concise Oxford Dictionary Of Literary Terms By K. Boldik And Some Uzbek Literary Dictionaries. *Scientific Reports Of Bukhara State University*, 115. https://buxdu.uz/media/jurnallar/ilmiy_axborot/ilmiy_axborot_5_son_2020.pdf#page=117.

77. Саидова, М. (2021). THE CONCISE OXFORD DICTIONARY OF LITERARY TERMS. ЛУЕАТИДАГИ ДРАМА АДАБИЙ ТУРИГА ХОС ТЕРМИНЛАРИНИНГ МАЗМУНИЙ ТАДЛИЛИ//ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. Uz),(8).https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/445

78. Saidova, M. U. (2020). LEXICOGRAPHIC AND ETHYMOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCISE OXFORD DICTIONARY OF LITERARY TERMS BY.<https://namdu.researchcommons.org/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?Article=2723&context=journal>.

79. Saidova, M. U. The problem of studying literary terms on figurative language.https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=ru&as_sdt=0,5&cluster=9219256601546054307.

80. Usmonova, Z. H. (2021). The peculiarity of fantastic works (on the example of the works of Ray Bradbury, Isaac Asimov and Stephen King). *European Scholar Journal*, 2(4), 499-503. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/394826-none-ac04ea4d.pdf>

81. Yuldasheva, f. (2023). Исследования вежливости в современной лингвистике. центр научных публикаций (buxdu.Uz), 31(31). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/9211.
82. Yuldasheva, f. (2023). Выражение вежливости в речевом этикете. центр научных публикаций (buxdu.Uz), 31(31). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/9214.
83. Yuldasheva Feruza Erkinovna. (2022). The Principle of Politeness in the English and Uzbek Languages. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 6, 65–70. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/erb/article/view/799>.
84. Zarina Habibovna Usmonova. (2021). THE PECULIARITY OF FANTASTIC WORKS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE WORKS OF RAY BRADBURY, ISAAC ASIMOV AND STEPHEN KING). *European Scholar Journal*, 2(4), 499-503. Retrieved from <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/esj/article/view/684>.
85. Гарунов М.Г., Пидкасистый П.И. Самостоятельная работа студентов. – М.: Знание, 1978. – 27 с
86. Донова И.И. Организация самостоятельной деятельности учащихся по иностранному языку // Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. – 2021. – № 11(79). – С. 222-225.
87. Саидова, Мухайё. "Inglizcha poetik terminlarning o'zbek tilida berilishida shakl va mazmun munosabati." ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. Uz) 13.13. (2022). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/6714.
88. Umidullayevna, Saidova Mukhayyo. "SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH POETIC TERMS IN LITERARY DICTIONARIES." RESEARCH AND EDUCATION 1.1 (2022): 38- <https://researchedu.org/index.php/re/article/view/682>.
89. Солиева, М. (2021). ASSESSING THE KNOWLEDGE OF STUDENTS ON THE MOODLE PLATFORM. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 1(1). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/2547.
90. Солиева, М. (2022). РЕЧЕВЫЕ ПРАВИЛА ЭТИКИ КАК ОБЪЕКТ ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 8(8). https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4858.

91. Щербакова Н.П. Самостоятельная работа и дидактические принципы ее организации // Новая наука: от идеи к результату. – 2015. – № 7. – С. 31-33

92. Шелепова М.Г. Самостоятельная работа как способ организации учебной деятельности // Наука, образование, общество: проблемы и перспективы развития. – 2013. – № 4. – С. 161-162.